

Original Article

ANTENATAL ANXIETY AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN ATTENDING SPECIALIST HOSPITAL SOKOTO, SOKOTO STATE

¹Auwalu Muhammed, ¹Waleeyat Abdulazeez and ²Ado Shehu

¹Department of Nursing Sciences, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, College of Health Sciences Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto

²Department of Nursing Sciences, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, ATBU, Bauchi

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20381185>

Abstract: Pregnancy is one of the most significant experiences in a woman's life, but it often brings psychological challenges such as mood swings, exhaustion, anxiety, and emotional disorders. This study explored the prevalence, impact, and risk factors associated with antenatal anxiety among pregnant women attending antenatal care at Specialist Hospital Sokoto, Nigeria. A hospital-based cross-sectional design was employed using systematic random sampling. A total of 150 structured questionnaires were distributed, and 144 were completed and returned. Findings revealed that 49.3% agreed and 27.1% strongly agreed experiencing worry or anxiety during pregnancy, highlighting the need for targeted support and interventions from healthcare providers. The perceived impacts reported were reduced enjoyment of activities (29.2%), irritability, feelings of detachment (15.3% often and 6.9% always), panic attacks (31.9%), and poor concentration (18.1% often and 16% always). Previous anxiety or depression (36.8%), lack of social support (6.3%) and concerns about fetal health (31.3% agreed and 27.1% strongly agreed) emerged as major risk factors. The study underscores the importance of addressing antenatal anxiety and implementing effective strategies to promote the psychological well-being of pregnant women in Sokoto.

Keywords: Antenatal anxiety, Pregnancy, Risk factors, Prevalence, Mental health, maternal health, Intervention, Prenatal care

Introduction

Pregnancy is a remarkable yet challenging experience, involving profound physical, emotional, and social changes (Ahmadi et al., 2019). Pregnant women, while preoccupied with fetal growth and future responsibilities, are vulnerable to psychological concerns such as mood swings, exhaustion, depression, and pregnancy-related anxiety (PRA) (Bjelica et al., 2018). PRA refers to anxiety specifically linked to pregnancy, including worries about labor, delivery, maternal and fetal health, healthcare availability, and parenting capacity (Huizink et al., 2004). Unlike general anxiety, PRA is more strongly associated with adverse outcomes

Original Article

such as preterm birth (<37 weeks) and low birth weight (Huizink et al., 2019). Preterm birth is especially prevalent in Africa and Asia, with Eastern Africa reporting rates as high as 14.3% (Beck et al., 2020).

Untreated PRA can have serious implications, including miscarriage, hypertension, shortened gestation, and developmental challenges such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and emotional difficulties in children (Field, 2017; Tomfohr-Madsen et al., 2019). Global prevalence ranges from 6–29% in high-income countries, 32% in South Asia, and 1–26% in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (Jill & Sunil, 2014; Jha et al., 2018; Rubertsson et al., 2017).

In Africa, studies have identified key risk factors for PRA, including low education, primigravidity, intimate partner violence, and poor social support (Beketie et al., 2021). Similarly, in Nigeria, prevalence rates range between 6.8% and 54%, with determinants including young maternal age, socio-economic disadvantage, previous abortions, difficult labor, poor social support, and psychosocial stressors (Kuo, 2014).

Antenatal anxiety not only increases maternal vulnerability to postpartum depression and mood disorders but is also linked to adverse outcomes for infants, including preterm birth, low birth weight, and long-term behavioral challenges (Bayrampour et al., 2016). Despite its burden, research on prevalences, perceived impact on maternal wellbeing, and risk factors remained limited in the study area to inform effective interventions and prevention strategies.

This study therefore seeks to investigate the prevalence and determinants of antenatal anxiety among pregnant women in Sokoto, Nigeria, and to explore its implications for maternal and child health outcomes. Findings are expected to inform the design of interventions and support systems that promote psychological well-being during pregnancy.

Aim

The aim of this research is to explore the prevalence, impact, and potential risk factors associated with antenatal anxiety among pregnant women attending specialist hospital Sokoto.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting

A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted among pregnant women attending antenatal care (ANC) at the Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology, and Perinatology, Specialist Hospital Sokoto, Sokoto State. The ANC clinic runs three times weekly, attending to about 150 women per day.

Study Population and Sampling

The study population included pregnant women aged 18–45 years across all trimesters who attended ANC during the study period. Women who were critically ill or declined participation were excluded.

The sample size of 150 was determined using a 13% prevalence rate from a previous national survey (NPC & ICF Macro, 2019), with a 5% precision level and a 95% anticipated response rate. A systematic random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation across age, socio-economic status, and gestational stage. A total of 150 women were selected, of which 144 completed the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire comprising four sections: 1

Socio-demographic information (age, marital status, religion, education, occupation).

Prevalence of antenatal anxiety (six items).

Impact of antenatal anxiety on maternal mental health and well-being (six items).

Potential risk factors for antenatal anxiety.

Original Article

The questionnaire was validated by two maternal health experts for face and content validity, with feedback incorporated. Reliability was assessed through pretesting and Pearson Product Moment Correlation, yielding a coefficient of 0.95, confirming high reliability.

Data Collection Procedure

Approval was obtained from the hospital management and maternity unit heads. Eligible women were provided with an information sheet, and the study objectives were explained. Written informed consent was obtained before participation. Questionnaires were administered in a private room within the ANC clinic, with clear instructions and assistance provided where necessary.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used to summarize categorical and continuous variables.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Specialist Hospital Research and Ethics Committee. Participants gave written informed consent after being briefed on the study objectives. Confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation were assured throughout the study.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics

Out of 144 respondents, 29.9% were aged 15–25 years, 53.5% were 26–35 years, and 16.7% were 36–45 years. All respondents were married. The majority (79.9%) were Muslims, while 20.1% were Christians. In terms of education, 19.4% had primary education or less, 44.4% had secondary education, and 36.1% attained tertiary education. Regarding occupation, 32.6% were employed, 44.4% unemployed, and 22.9% classified as “others.”

Prevalence of antenatal anxiety

Almost half of the respondents (49.3%) agreed and 27.1% strongly agreed that they often felt worried or anxious during pregnancy. Over one-third (37.5%) reported difficulty sleeping due to anxiety, while 25% disagreed. Feelings of restlessness were less frequent, with 31.3% strongly disagreeing. About 28.5% were neutral on feeling overwhelmed, while 22.2% agreed. Difficulty concentrating was reported by 33.3% agreeing and 11.8% strongly agreeing.

Perceived impact on maternal mental health

A considerable proportion (29.2%) often and 9.7% always experienced reduced enjoyment in activities. Feelings of detachment were reported by 15.3% often and 6.9% always. Difficulty bonding with the baby was uncommon, as 53.5% reported never experiencing it. Panic attacks were reported sometimes by 31.9% of respondents. Difficulties with concentration or decision-making were noted by 18.1% often and 16% always. Thoughts of self-harm were rare, with 66.7% never experiencing them.

Potential risk factors

Most respondents (74.3%) strongly disagreed with having a family history of mental illness, though 36.8% strongly agreed to a history of previous anxiety or depression. Lack of social support was reported by only 6.3%. Concerns about the baby’s health were common, with 31.3% agreeing and 27.1% strongly agreeing. Experiences of physical abuse during pregnancy were reported by 19.4%.

Original Article

Discussion

This study found a high prevalence of antenatal anxiety among pregnant women in Sokoto, particularly among those aged 26–35 years. Although all respondents were married, which differs from some international findings (Goyal et al., 2012), marital status appears to influence anxiety differently across cultural contexts.

The prevalence observed is comparable to reports from Korea and the Netherlands (Lee et al., 2017; Loos et al., 2013). Antenatal anxiety is clinically significant, as it has been linked to adverse outcomes including preterm birth, low birth weight, and impaired child development (Huizink et al., 2006; Leiferman, 2012).

Respondents reported symptoms such as restlessness and reduced enjoyment in activities, consistent with prior studies (Faisal-Cury et al., 2020; Smith & Ford, 2018). Some also reported emotional detachment, difficulty bonding, and panic attacks, highlighting the need for psychosocial support. Reassuringly, most respondents did not report thoughts of self-harm, aligning with earlier findings of lower suicidal ideation in pregnancy (Ross et al., 2015).

Key risk factors identified were lack of social support (Huizink et al., 2006; Bayrampour et al., 2016), concerns about fetal health (Li et al., 2019; Saravanan et al., 2020), and experiences of physical abuse (Sigala et al., 2020). Addressing these through routine screening, health education, and supportive interventions could reduce anxiety and improve maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Conclusion

This study revealed a high prevalence of antenatal anxiety among pregnant women in Sokoto, particularly in the 26–35-year age group. While all respondents were married, marital status appeared to influence anxiety differently than in other contexts. Most participants reported worry, irritability, and difficulty concentrating, with some experiencing challenges in bonding or emotional well-being. Key risk factors included lack of social support and concerns about fetal health. These findings underscore the need for routine screening, targeted interventions, and psychosocial support to promote maternal mental health and improve pregnancy outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Ahmadi, A., MoosaviSahebalzamani, S., Ghavami, F. and Shafiee, Y. F. (2019). Effects of psychological interventions on postpartum depression, anxiety and infants' weight in primipara women. *Preventive Care in Nursing and Midwifery Journal*, 4:19–31.
- Bayrampour, H., Ali, E. and McNeil, D. A. (2016). Benzodiazepine use during pregnancy and adverse neonatal outcomes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Canadian journal of psychiatry. Revue canadienne de psychiatrie*, 61(7), 385-394.
- Beketie, E. D., Kahsay, H., Nigussie, F. G., & Tafese, W. T. (2021). Magnitude and associated factors of antenatal depression among mothers attending antenatal care in Arba Minch town, Ethiopia, 2018. *PLoS ONE*, 16(12), e0261088. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0261088>
- Bjelica, A., Cetkovic, N. and Trninic-Pjevic, A. (2018). The phenomenon of pregnancy—a psychological view. *Ginekologia Polska*, 89:102–6. doi: 10.5603/GP.a2018.0017
- Beck, S., Wojdyla, D., Say, L., Betran, A. P., Merialdi, M. and Requejo, J. H. (2010). The worldwide incidence of preterm birth: a systematic review of maternal mortality and morbidity. *Bulletin of World Health Organization*, 88:31–8.

Original Article

- Faisal-Cury, A., Menezes, P. R., and Bressan, R. A. (2020). Prevalence of anxiety and depression during pregnancy in a private setting sample. *Archives of Women's Mental Health*, 23(1), 83-87.
- Field, T. (2017) prenatal anxiety effects: a review. *Infant Behavior and Development*, 49:120– 8.
- Goyal, D, Gay, C, and Lee, K. A. (2012). How much does marital status matter in maternal health? *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 16(1), 86-94
- Huizink, A. C., Delforterie, M. J., Scheinin, N. M., Tolvanen, M., Karlsson, L., Karlsson, H. (2016). Adaption of pregnancy anxiety questionnaire–revised for all pregnant women regardless of parity: PRAQ-R2. *Archives of Women's Mental Health*, 19:125– 32. doi: 10.1007/s00737-015-0531-2
- Jha, S., Salve, H. R., Goswami, K., Sagar, R. and Kant, S. (2018). Burden of common mental disorders among pregnant women: a systematic review. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 36:46–53. doi: 10.1016/j.ajp.2018.06.020
- Jill, F. K. and Sunil, T. S. (2014). Perceived social stress, pregnancy-related anxiety, depression and subjective social status among pregnant Mexican and Mexican American Women in South Texas. *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved*, 25:546– 61.
- Kuo, S. H. (2014). Antenatal depression and anxiety: Women's experiences and need for support. *Journal of midwifery and women's health*, 59(4), 389-396.
- Lee, A. M., Lam, S. K., SzeMun Lau, S. M., Chong, C. S., Chui, H. W., and Fong, D. Y. (2007). Prevalence, course, and risk factors for antenatal anxiety and depression. *Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 110(5), 1102-1112.
- Leiferman, J. A. (2012). The effect of maternal depressive symptoms on maternal behaviors associated with child health. *Health Education and Behavior*, 39(4), 403-411.
- Li, Y., Yu, Y., Luo, X., and Wang, C. (2019). Risk factors for prenatal anxiety and depression in Shanghai pregnant women. *General Psychiatry*, 32(1), e100056. doi: 10.1136/gpsych-2019-100056
- Loos, M., van Aken, M. A., van der Veen, R., Junger, M., Woltering, S., Häge, A., Tharner, A., and Klein, V. (2013). The relation between maternal anxiety during pregnancy and early childhood cognitive functioning: the Generation R Study. *Child Development*, 84(5), 1557-1570.
- National Population Commission (Nigeria) & ICF Macro. (2019). *Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018: Key Indicators Report*. Abuja, Nigeria & Rockville, Maryland, USA. <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR359/FR359.pdf>
- Ross, L. E., Grigoriadis, S., Mamisashvili, L., Vonderporten, E. H., Roerecke, M., Rehm, J., ... and Dennis, C. L. (2015). Selected pregnancy and delivery outcomes after exposure to antidepressant medication: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA psychiatry*, 72(4), 335-343.

Original Article

Rubertsson, C., Hellström, J., Cross, M. and Sydsjo, G. (2014). Anxiety in early pregnancy: prevalence and contributing factors. *Archives of Women’s Mental Health*, 17:221–8.

Saravanan, A., Ramanan, P., Shanmuganath, J., and Rajkumar, S. (2020). Prevalence of antenatal anxiety and depression and its association with other pregnancy-related factors: A cross-sectional study in a tertiary care hospital setup. *Journal of Pharmacy and Bioallied Sciences*, 12(1), 373-378.

Singala, D., Chateau, D. and Struck, S. (2020). In utero antidepressants and neurodevelopmental outcomes in kindergarteners. *Pediatric*, 145(5): e20191157.

Smith, M. V., and Ford, J. D. (2018). Multiclass patterns of anxiety symptoms during pregnancy and associations with child cognitive development and mental health in early life. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 172(10), 966-974.

Tomfohr-Madsen, L., Cameron, E. E., DunkelSchetter, C., Campbell, T., O’Beirne, M. and Letourneau, N. (2019). Pregnancy anxiety and preterm birth: the moderating role of sleep. *Health and Psychology*, 38:1025–35. doi: 10.1037/hea0000792

Table 1: Socio-demography

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Valid percent
Age Group			
15-25	43	29.9	29.9
26-35	77	53.5	53.5
36-45	24	16.7	16.7
Total	144	100	100
Marital Status			
Single	0	0	0
Married	144	100	100
Divorced	0	0	0
Widow	0	0	0
Total	144	100	100
Religion			Valid percent
Christianity	29	20.1	20.1
Islam	115	79.9	79.9
Others	0	0	0
Total	144	100	100
Education Level			
Primary or Less	28	19.4	19.4
Secondary	64	44.4	44.4
Tertiary	52	36.1	36.1
Total	144	100	100
Occupational Status			

Original Article

Employed	47	32.6	32.6
Unemployed	64	44.4	44.4
Others	33	22.9	22.9
Total	200	100	100

Table 2: Prevalence of Antenatal Anxiety

Variable	SD	D	N	A	SA
I often feel worried or anxious during my pregnancy	15(10.4)	19(13.2)	0	71(49.3)	39(27.1)
I often have difficulty sleeping due to worry or anxiety about my pregnancy	19(13.2)	36(25)	16(11.1)	54(37.5)	19(13.2)
I often feel restless or on edge during my pregnancy	45(31.3)	34(23.6)	29(20.1)	19(13.2)	17(11.8)
I often feel overwhelmed or unable to cope with the demands of my pregnancy	23(16)	48(33.3)	41(28.5)	32(22.2)	0
I frequently feel irritable or on edge during my pregnancy	40(27.8)	19(13.2)	23(16)	46(31.9)	16(11.1)
I often have difficulty concentrating or forget things related to my pregnancy	39(27.1)	29(20.1)	11(7.6)	48(23.3)	17(11.8)

Key: SD= strongly disagreed, D=Disagreed, N=Neutral, A=Agreed and SA=strongly agreed

Table 3: Impact of Antenatal Anxiety on Maternal Mental Health and Wellbeing

Variable	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Difficulty enjoying activities or feeling pleasure during pregnancy	61(42.4)	0	27(18.8)	42(29.2)	14(9.7)
Feeling detached or emotionally numb during pregnancy	82(56.9)	12(8.3)	18(12.5)	22(15.3)	10(6.9)
Difficulty bonding with the baby during pregnancy	77(53.5)	29(20.1)	26(18.1)	0	12(8.3)
Experiencing panic attacks during pregnancy	39(27.1)	59(41)	46(31.9)	0	0
Difficulty concentrating or making decisions during pregnancy	47(32.6)	30(20.8)	18(12.5)	26(18.1)	23(16)
Thoughts of self-harm or suicide during pregnancy	96(66.7)	27(18.8)	21(14.6)	0	0

Original Article

Table 4: Potential Risk Factors

Variable	SD	D	N	A	SA
I have a family history of mental health disorders	107(74.3)	14(9.7)	19(13.2)	4(2.8)	0
I have experienced previous episodes of anxiety or depression	28(19.4)	11(7.6)	37(25.7)	15(10.4)	53(36.8)
I lack social support during my pregnancy	49(34)	34(23.6)	52(36.1)	9(6.3)	0
I have concerns about the health of my baby	0	32(22.2)	28(19.4)	45(31.3)	39(27.1)
I have experienced physical abuse or violence during my pregnancy	12(8.3)	44(30.6)	60(41.7)	28(19.4)	0

Key: SD= Strongly disagreed, D=Disagreed, N=Neutral, A=Agreed and SA= Strongly agreed